

Let's Do It Together

User involvement in output checks at the Research Data Centre

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Abstract

The Research Data Centre (FDZ) of the Federal Employment Agency (BA) at the Institute for Employment Research (IAB) provides external researchers with access to microdata in the field of labour market research. In order to guarantee data protection, checking the statistical confidentiality of analysis results generated as part of controlled remote data processing is a central service of the FDZ. Growing numbers of users and increasing design options for the presentation of results are tying up more and more resources for this task. In the 21 years since the FDZ was founded, it has repeatedly implemented measures to standardise and speed up processes. Output control is currently carried out using a mix of automation, manual control and user involvement. We would like to present the various output control measures and focus in particular on the stronger involvement of users, which has been implemented since the beginning of 2024. A stronger involvement of users and corresponding guidelines are also essential for use of data via remote desktop access in the future.

Keywords: data protection, data access, output control

Resources

Guidelines that support users in the design of their analysis programmes:
https://doku.iab.de/fdz/access/Guidelines_en.pdf

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References